

The Concept of Aadhi or Mental Illness According to Yoga Darshan

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Abstract:

While we find numerous descriptions of aadhi or mental illness throughout Indian scriptures, the *Yoga Sutras of Patanjali*, also known as the *Yoga Darshan*, considered as the central text of the philosophical school of yoga, makes scarce reference to given condition. In the present article I analyse the relationship between the *yog'antarayas*, also known as obstacles in yoga, described in Patanjali's work, and the development and experience of aadhi. These *antarayas*, in posterior commentaries of the *Yoga Sutras* written by authorities like sage Vyasa and Vachaspati Mishra, are classified into two categories, one of the nature of *chitta bhumi* and the other of the nature of *vrtti*. In consequence, aadhi can be considered as the manifest expression of given dysfunctional or detrimental forms of *chitta bhumi* -*mudha* and *kshipta*- and *vrtti* -*viparyaya* and *klishatah*-.

Key Words: Aadhi, mental illness, *yog'antarayas*, yoga darshan, *chitta bhumi*, *chitta vrtti*.

1. INTRODUCTION

Ādhi -or *aadhi*-, is the Sanskrit term most commonly used across yogic and related literature to refer to mental illness or disorders as a whole. In the *Yoga Vasistha* (Mishra, 2010, p. 32; Venkatesananda, 2010, p. 295), aadhi is employed to address conditions such as mental disequilibrium or disorder, psychological disturbance, or conditioned psyche and is described, along with *vyādhi* -physical disease/malady-, as one of the sources of sorrow and obstacles to *samadhi*. Similar reference we see in the *Harikathamrutasara*, where Sri Jagannāthadāsa (1995, v. 31) appeals to the removal of adhi and vyadhi or their combined form, *upatala*, for cognitive and emotional well-being. The co-occurrence of physical and mental problems is frequently pointed out in scriptural references to psychopathology, nonetheless, we also do find recurrent approaches from the cognitive perspective like those in the *Skanda purana* (Tagare, 1993, p. 432) where the prevention of mental illness or mental suffering -adhi- is advised through the means of knowledge. This method for the prevention of suffering is also taught by Patanjali in the sutras II.16,17 where the removal of *heya* is explained. Across contemporary yogic literature we find adhi commonly addressed together with vyadhi and *upadhi* -constraints, limitations-, conforming a triad known as *triya taat* (Gupta, 1993, p. 42). These three components of the *triya taat* are antagonistic to *samadhi* (AYUSH, 2021), the state of ultimate mental health (Bhagwan, 2015), which is required for the achievement of *kaivalya* or final liberation.

The science of ayurveda, very closely related to yoga, as concerned with medical and health matters, studies in depth the subject of mental disorders or *manovikara* (Ramu & Venkataram, 1985). It is so, that throughout the several ayurvedic texts, topics like the pathogenesis of mental disease -*manasaroga samprapti*-, aetiology -*manoroga nidana*-, symptomatology -*manasaroga laksha*-, classification -*manasavikara vargeekarana*- or treatment -*unmada chikitsa*- are dealt with in detail (K. Gupta & Mamidi, 2020; H.K & Sukumar, 2020; J.S. & Y. S., 2020). Another term generally used in reference to mental illness in the field of ayurveda is the concept of *unmada*. Charaka defines unmada (Acharya, 1941, p.223) as the unsettled condition of *manas* -mind-, *buddhi* -decision/intellect-, *smriti* -memory-, *bhakti* -desire-, *chesta* -psychomotricity-, *sanjnana* -orientation and responsiveness-, *achara* -conduct- and *shila* -temperament and habits-. While *manovikara* and *unmada* are many times used interchangeably, *unmada* is considered as the causal condition for *manovikara*, being the former the pathologic condition and the later the consequential form (or forms) of mental disfunction (Ramu et al., 1988). *Unmada* is classified into six categories; out of these, five are the manifest result of biological causes such as disturbed *dosha* or intoxication, and one, *adhi*, corresponds to the type caused by mental afflictions (Meulenbeld et al., 2011, p. 15).

In the *Yoga Darshan* (Bharati, 1986; Jha, 1894; Legget, 1990; Satyananda, 1976; Vivekananda, 1896), primarily concerned with spiritual development and achievement of *kaivalya*, less importance has been given to the naming and classification of physical and mental illnesses, considering them, as a whole, as obstacles in the achievement of yoga's goal. For the same reason, while the causes of these obstacles and their concomitant symptoms are treated in depth, we do not find explicit mention to *adhi* or mental disorders per se. Nonetheless, allusions to disturbed and dysfunctional conditions of the mind are numerous and, in addition, relying on the expected knowledge of grammar of his pupils/readers, leads us to believe that the specific mention of *adhi* was considered by Patanjali as redundant or unnecessary given its conspicuity.

2. AADHI, SAMADHI AND THE YOG'ANTARAYAS

The terms *aadhi* and *samadhi* -as well as *vyadhi* and *upadhi*- share the same lexical root, “-*dhi*” commonly translated as consciousness, *buddhi* or intellect (Monier-Williams, 2014; Sturgess, 2014) The prefix “*sama*-” indicates balance, equilibrium or perfection (Monier-Williams, 2014; Patel et al., 2018) signifying so the term *samadhi* as the highest or perfect state of consciousness. On the other hand, the prefix “*a*-” is used in Sanskrit to indicate negation (ibid.) and can be used, according to context, to denote absence or opposition. By this rule, *aadhi* applies to the state of absence or opposition of consciousness and intellect, the unnatural or corrupt form of *buddhi*, a state which is opposite to *samadhi* or perfection of consciousness. It should be noted that an alternate etymological analysis of the term *samadhi*, divides the term as “*sam*-” -meaning togetherness, integration, uniformity- and “-*adhi*” -defined as to be established- whereas the inferred meaning of the significant in this context applies to the same meaning previously defined, to be fully established in consciousness.

In the first chapter of the *Yoga Sutras* (I.30,31), sage Patanjali enumerates the conditions which cause the obstruction of the process and achievement of yoga -*yog'antarayas*-, named as

the *chittavikshepas* and *vikshepa-sahabhuvah*. The aim of the yogic discipline is to reach kaivalya, the establishment of the Self in its real nature of pure consciousness. For this, the mind has to be transcended through *vrtti nirodhah*, reaching the state of samadhi by the development of concentration -*dharana*- and meditation -*dhyana*-. The *chittavikshepas* or “distractors of chitta” together with their natural or concomitant symptoms/correlates -*vikshepa-sahabhuvah*- impede the concentration of the mind, hampering so the achievement of the consequent required stages for the progression and success in yoga. Additionally, sage Vyasa distinctively indicates (Aranya, 1983, p. 70) these obstacles to be the cause of psychological disturbances and impairment, or in other words, of *aadhi* or mental disorders. The presence of *yog’antarayas* is not restricted to those suffering from mental disorders, being also commonly found among mentally healthy population. The difference between both populations radicates in the intensity of these conditions, being for those experiencing mental illness, of the strength necessary to cause cognitive, emotional, behavioral and functional disturbances and/or impairment (Gupta, 2005).

Figure 1

Diagram representing the relationship between Aadhi and the Yog’antarayas

2.1 Chitta Vikshepas: the distractors of chitta

The first *vikshepa* mentioned in the sutras (I.30) is *vyādhi* or physical illness/disease. Vyasa specifies *vyadhi* as the disturbance of the equilibrium of the *dhatu*s and the *rasa*s, ayurvedic terminology for the physical constituents of the body, including all the 11 systems of the body. He also mentions as part of *vyadhi* the dysfunction of the *karana*s, which some authors have translated as the physical organs of the body or organs of the senses (Prasada, 2003; Raja, 1852) while other extend its meaning to the *antahkarana* of *samkhya* (S. V. Bharati, 1986).

Although vyadhi is primarily restricted to biological aspects, it holds an inexorable correlation with several aspects of the psyche where disease or malfunction of systems like the nervous or endocrine, for example, are directly correlated with the presence of numerous mental disorders (APA, 2013; WHO, 1992). In scriptures previous and contemporary to the *Yoga sutras*, there is a recurrent exposition of the hierarchy of causation between adhi and vyadhi, being physical illness considered -when not caused by physical means- as a consequence of aadhi or mental illness (Majewski & Bhavanani, 2020, p. 31; Sudhā, 1988; Tagare, 1993; Venkatesananda, 2010). In addition, the existence of vyadhi, characterized by physical pain and malfunction, is inevitably accompanied by the formation of vrttis and a disturbed mind -aadhi-, which causes the impossibility of concentration and restriction of chitta (Aranya, 1983).

The next impairing factor in the concentration of chitta is *styāna*. There is not an accurate English term which can define *styāna* with exactitude, reason by which we find multiple terms used in its attempted translation such as dullness, languor, mental idleness or apathy among others. *Styāna* is the mind's indisposition to work (Prasada, 2003, p. 53), a state of exhaustion or "chronic fatigue" how (Taimni, 1961, p. 76) calls it, in which the individual lacks the necessary energy -reflected in aspects such as drive, motivation, vitality, etc.- to engage into action. Described by Swami H. Aranya (1983, p. 71) as a state of mental incapacity or incompetence, *styāna* applies primarily to covert behavior, negatively influencing the different actions or performance of the mental functions, including from the active focus of attention to processes like thinking or emotional engagement. In the -overt- behavioral dimension *styāna* implies low levels of volition and conative output (Bharati, 1986, p. 325).

Styana, as described in the previous paragraph, is a form of dysfunction common to tamasic states -*mudha*- but not exclusive. In a further explanation of Vyasa's commentary, Bharati states that *styana* can also occur when the mind has become habituated to restlessness or a state of non-concentration what reflects in the indisposition and avoidance of goal-oriented action (Bharati, 1986, p.326).

Samsaya, commonly translated as doubt, corresponds with the state of uncertainty based in indecision and/or lack of sufficient knowledge. Shankaracharya (Legget, 1990, p. 137) defines *samsaya* as "the idea embracing both alternatives"; similarly, Vyasa uses the metaphor "*samsaya* is a kind of thinking touching both sides" (Aranya, 1983, p. 71) to denote the mind's oscillation between two options, resumable in general terms by the duality correct/true/right-incorrect/false/wrong (Arya, 1986, p. 327). Vachaspati Mishra adds to Vyasa's interpretation (ibid.), a note on the strong interfering role of *samsaya*, along with *bhrāntidarśana* -or confusion of philosophies-, in the restriction of *vrtti* or *vrttinirodhah*, and therefore the importance of its eradication.

Pramāda, defined as procrastination, carelessness or negligence is characterized by the lack of will or interest in the exertion of effort (Prasada, 2003) and attention (Raja, 1852). From the spiritual or yogic perspective *pramāda* implies the failure in the practice of *bhavana* and commitment to the precepts of yoga (S. V. Bharati, 1986); extended to the psychological aspects, it is antagonistic to the *shat-sampat* (Bhatta & Abhyankar, 1917), namely *shama* -quietude-, *dama* -

restraint-, *uparati* -withdrawal from worldly involvements-, *titaksha* -forbearance-, *shraddha* -faith, humility- and *samadhana* -freedom from conflicts-. *Pramāda* can be caused by the passions arisen from rajasic influence (Bharati, 1986) as well as by the inertia and heaviness of *tamas* (Prasada, 2003).

Sloth or *ālasya* is a characteristic feature of *mudha bhumi* (Aranya, 1983) and takes expression in the shape of laziness and indolence. Its effects on the psychological functions resemble those of *styāna* but they both divert in cause and form. *Styāna* produces inability of the mind by physical conditions while *ālasya* develops through choice or habit -psychological conditions- (Taimni, 1961). Swami H. Aranya defines *ālasya* as the reluctance or indisposition to engage in devotional practice on the account of dullness of body and mind. Those suffering from *alasya* rejoice in inaction or lack the interest or motivation to engage and act.

The state of constant longing towards sensorial experience and pleasure derived of it is known as *avirati*. Commonly translated as craving, *avirati* comprises the inner attitude of non-abstention (Bharati, 1986, p.327) directed by desire and *raga-vasanas* and implies as well the failure to withdraw from sensual stimuli (Legget, 1990), the weakness against the drive for involvement, indulgence. Several commentaries of the *Yoga Sutras* (Jha, 1907; Taimni, 1961) define *avirati* as “worldly-mindedness” in regard of the disposition towards the engagement with worldly (materialistic) matters, a condition described by Lord Krishna in the *Bhagavad Gita* as “dwelling in the middle” (Sivananda, 2000, v. XIV.18) and attributed to *rajo guna* thus *kshipta bhumi*. Feuerstein (1989) explains the effect of *avirati* on attention as dissipating, meaning its dispersion or fragmentation by the engagement of attention with multiple objects. Bharati considers *avirati* as the opposite of *uparati* (p.327), the withdrawal from worldly interests happening in the first stage of *vairagya*. It is interesting to note for the purpose of this research, the direct mention of addiction in various texts as part of *avirati*’s definition; Bhoja Raja (1852, p. 36) explains it as “addiction to objects” consisting on the attachment of *chitta* to the objects of the senses or Swami H. Aranya (1986, p.71) as the addiction or thirst for worldly objects causing non-abstention.

Bhrāntidarśana is a composite term formed by the Sanskrit words “*bhranti*” meaning false, and “*darshana*” translated as philosophy, views or perception (S. J. Bharati, 2007) and is therefore often defined as “confusion of philosophies”. In *bhrāntidarśana* one is established in wrong knowledge, attributing truth or reality to that which does not correspond with the real nature of the concept or object (Arya, 1986). Furthermore, the *Yoga-sudhakara* adds to the meaning of this concept, the apprehension of that -object- which is not there (p.327), similar notion to that of hallucinations in psychiatric terminology. Narayana Tirtha, in the “*Yoga-sidhanta-chandrika* and *Sutrartha-bodhini*” (ibid.) relates *bhrāntidarśana* as a possible consequence of *samsaya*, where in the absence of oscillation, one has settled in the false or incorrect option. While both -doubt and error- belong to the category of *viparyaya*, Vyasa (Prasada, 2003) and Shankaracharya (Legget, 1990) name the later as *viparyaya jnana* and direct the reader to the *sutra* I.8 to further understand the nature of cognitive or perceptual error.

Alabdhabhūmikatva is the inability to concentrate (Vivekananda, 2003) or to achieve finer states (Jha, 1907; Legget, 1990). From a psychological perspective, *alabdhabhūmikatva* corresponds to -the category of symptoms known as- distractibility; the sutras do not specify the form or causes for this state, posteriorly clarifying Bhoja Raja (1852) that by any cause and in any form, failure to attain concentration is *alabdhabhūmikatva*. In relation to yoga and the purification of chitta, *alabdhabhūmikatva* refers to the inability to progress towards higher states of yoga and consciousness (Prasada, 2003) -directly dependent on concentrating ability- and the consequent stagnancy in lower stages of spiritual evolution.

Anavasthitatva or instability, is closely related to *alabdhabhūmikatva* and causes the recession from achieved improvement -finer states- (S. V. Bharati, 1986; Prasada, 2003). This degradation applies to the concentrating abilities as well as to the loss of the state of concentration -*dharana*- and its consequent forms of meditation and *samadhi*. While most commentaries resume the meaning of *anavasthitatva* to the degradation of the progress in yoga and concentration, in the knowledge that the quality of attention affects, directly or indirectly, all the processes of the psyche as well as the correlations existing between the states of chitta and attention, the term instability is thus by extension applicable to any psychological -and behavioral- aspect. The cause of this lack of stability and its form of expression will depend from the contextual *bhumi* -*kshipta* or *mudha*- in which it occurs.

2.2 Vikshepasahabhuvah: the concomitant conditions to the distractors of chitta

Dukha -dukham or *duḥkha*- is the Sanskrit term that denotes any kind of pain, unhappiness or suffering. Direct reference to *dukha* is found across multiple yogic and related texts such as the Upanishads, the Yoga Sutras or the Bhagavad Gita, and is equally addressed by the Pali term *dukkha* in Buddhist literature and tradition (Takeda, 1985). In the context of the yog'antarayas, Swami Vivekananda (2003) and Bhoja Raja (1852) explain that *dukha* applies to the suffering of psychological nature -“mental distress”-, what includes any type of negative emotion or subjective experience. As described by Lord Krishna in the Bhagavad Gita (Dass, 2012, v. 2.56), and in the Samkhya Karika (Mainkar, 2004), suffering can be of three types (Aranya, 1983):

- *Adhyatmika*, internal to oneself, of physical -disease- and mental -passions and desires- nature.
- *Adhibhautika*, caused or inflicted by another subject, creature or object
- *Adhidaivika*, caused by natural factors or calamity

Vyasa points out (Arya, 1986) that regardless of the previous classification, the experience of pain and suffering consists of a mental event driven ultimately by desire, and is therefore closely linked, yet not restricted, with the action of *rajas* and *kshipta bhumi*; at the presence of *dukha*, the mind is prevented to surpass *vikshipta bhumi* and reach *ekagra* or concentrated mind.

Daurmanasya is a Sanskrit term composed of the prefix “*dur-*”, meaning ill or bad, and the word “*manas*” or mind and which literally translates as bad or ill-minded. It is the antonym of *saumanasya*, “good or happy mindedness” (Bharati, 1986, p.331) what defines its meaning to any non-good or non-happy state, in other words, any negative affective state or mood.

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Daurmanasya can take many kinds of expression, all of them causes or forms of distress (Raja, 1852). This antaraya includes all the moods of negative valence such as sadness, depression, anxiety, anger, etc., as well as those on the extremes of the arousal spectrum -regardless of their valence- taking as an example manic or expansive mood in the ranges of extreme activation or languor and apathy for the opposite extreme (Aranya, 1983; Venkatesananda, 2010). Additionally, unstable mood and affective states characterized by emotional disturbances and dysregulation do also fall under the category of daurmanasya (Bharati, 1986, p.331).

As a state of chitta, the presence of daurmanasya is caused by guna and therefore, is not reliant on klesha for its occurrence. Nevertheless, daurmanasya promotes the exaltation of klesha and the consequent manifestation of klishtah vrttis; similarly, klishtah vrttis may trigger the occurrence of daurmanasya (Aranya, 1983; Raja, 1852). Sage Vyasa argues that one of the main triggers of daurmanasya, which he describes as “agitation of the mind” (Jha, 1907, p. 30), is the non-fulfilment of desire, which would cause a mood of irritation and despair.

Āngamejayatva, commonly defined as restlessness, shaking of the body or unsteadiness of the limbs is a feature of kshipta bhumi (Bharati, 1986) and is characterized by agitation or trembling (Jha, 1907) of the body. We should keep into perspective that chitta is considered as material and therefore as -the subtlest- part of the body. When different commentators specify the physical dimension of *āngamejayatva*, they do so to remark agitation by physical means -guna-, as opposite to emotional or psychological agitation which would belong to daurmanasya antaraya. This physical agitation, caused by rajoguna, manifests in all the physical aspects of the subject, from the movement of limbs to the state of chitta, and translates so to the psychological processing. This effect can also happen in the opposite direction, starting with a state of daurmanasya that causes the appearance of *āngamejayatva* (Aranya, 1983).

Śvāsaprasāvāsā is the combination of *shvasa* and *pra-shvasa*, meaning involuntary inhalation and exhalation respectively. When the condition of *śvāsaprasāvāsā* is present, the breathing process occurs in an unnatural and uncontrolled manner; agitated, weak, irregular, etc. Given the close relationship existing between breath and the state and flow of prana (Muktibodhananda et al., 2009), and between prana and the mental state (R. Vivekananda, 2008) when breath is altered, so is chitta. In fact, in the sutras II.49-53, Patanjali explains how through the control of inhalation and exhalation, prana can be controlled -pranayama- and the mind mastered. It is for this reason that although *śvāsaprasāvāsā* is in itself not a state of chitta, their inexorable correlation and by the criteria of *satkaryavada* -as with *vyadhi* and *āngamejayatva*-, Vachaspatimishra classifies it as a feature of chitta bhumi.

3. A BI-DIMENSIONAL CLASSIFICATION

Sage Vyasa and Vachaspati Mishra, authors of two of the most relevant commentaries of the *Yoga Sutras*, explain in their analysis of sutras I.30,31 (Arya, 1986; S. V. Bharati, 1986; Jha, 1907; Prasada, 2003) that according to their nature, the yog’antarayas can be categorized in two groups. The first category is comprised of those antarayas which represent pathological aspects of

chitta bhumi that occur, unequivocally accompanied or followed by related chitta vrttis. The second type of yog'antaraya is conformed by those which are in-themselves, vrttis.

The states of chitta, known in yoga philosophy as chitta bhumi, refer to the condition in which chitta is found at a certain moment and which influences not only the cognitive, affective and behavioral states of the mind but any process and experience taking place in it. As a material entity derived from the evolution of prakrti, chitta is essentially composed of the three gunas and its state is directly dependent on their configuration. These states, ordered by their conductivity for concentration, and consequently achievement of the state of yoga, are known as *Mudha*, *Kshipta*, *Vikshipta*, *Ekagra* and *Niruddha* (Arya, 1986; Jha, 1907, v. I.1,2). Out of the five forementioned, kshipta and mudha bhumi, caused by the dominance of tamoguna and rajoguna respectively, are considered as non-conductive for yoga and give rise, when overly expressed, to the appearance of aadhi and related symptoms. Conversely, chitta vrttis, translated with concepts such as fluctuations of chitta (Feuerstein, 1989) or mental modifications (Vireswarananda, 1936, v. 1.1.2), are the functional units of chitta by which cognition and the subjective experience occur. In psychological terms, chitta vrttis include mental events like thoughts, memories, imaginations, emotions, impulses, etc.

As shown in “Criteria 2” of Figure 2, Vyasa and Vachaspati Mishra classify the antarayas *vyādhi*, *styāna*, *pramāda*, *ālasya*, *avirati*, *alabdhabhūmikatva* and *alabdhabhūmikatva* -belonging to the chitta vikshepa group- and *daurmanasya*, *aṅgamejayatva* and *śvāsapraśvāsā* -of vikshepa-sahabhuvah category- as dysfunctional state-forms of chitta caused by excess of rajas and/or tamas, and thus pertinent to mudha and kshipta bhumis. These pathological forms of chitta bhumi influence the formation of vrtti and are thus accompanied by vrttis of the same pathological nature, which along with their related symptoms, impede the concentration of chitta and the progress towards the higher states of ekagra and niruddha.

Figure 2

Diagram representing Vachaspati’s classification of the yog’antarayas

Note: (a) causal nexus, (b) necessary cooccurrence

As vrttis per se, and those who accompany the former bhumis, Vachaspati Mishra (Bharati, 1986, pp. 325–327) explicitly classifies the chitta vikshepas *saṁśaya* and *bhrāntidarśana*. Corresponding respectively to the cognitive dysfunctions of doubt/confusion and erroneous information, both belong to the category of viparyaya vrtti or wrong knowledge. The viparyaya category of vrttis includes all those vrttis which result from impairment of the cognitive functions. Furthermore, he implies that dukha, or suffering, being necessarily experienced through chitta vrtti, corresponds and represents klishta vrttis and belongs therefore to the category of “vrttis in themselves” responsible of aadhi.

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4. CONCLUSION

While the Yoga Darshan places little emphasis in the detailed explanation of mental illness by considering aadhi as another form of obstacle in the achievement of kaivalya or yoga's goal, sage Patanjali does however describe the main factors leading to given condition. These factors, which he addresses as the yog'antarayas or hindrances in the path of yoga, are essentially resumed as conditions causing the distractions of the mind or chitta, which, when exacerbated, do not only prevent the achievement of samadhi but also prompt the pathological aspects of aadhi.

In view of the different descriptions of aadhi and its causative factors given throughout yogic literature we can conclude that aadhi or mental illness is the result of the dysfunctional states of chitta, mudha and kshipta bhumi, and their associated chitta vrttis. According to Yoga Darshan, the pathological dimensions of chitta bhumi can be divided in ten basic forms or traits, all having their tamasic and rajasic variants, with the exceptions of ālasya -exclusively tamasic- and aṅgamejayatva -exclusively rajasic-. Additionally, the vrttis involved in the development of mental illness and their experienced symptomatology are all, ultimately, of the viparyaya and klišhtah categories.

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